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PECULIARITIES OF MODELING BUSINESS PROCESSES OF AN ENTERPRISE IN THE CONTEXT OF INTERNATIONAL ACTIVITY

To ensure a competitive position, Ukrainian enterprises need to constantly adapt, change and improve their business processes in line with modern requirements and customer needs. Optimisation of business processes is a set of interrelated management, organisational and information measures, united by a certain technology, aimed at improving the parameters of both individual processes and the performance of the enterprise as a whole in order to meet the needs and expectations of stakeholders [1].

The need to adapt the business processes of Ukrainian enterprises to the requirements of the international market is particularly acute and relevant in the context of structural restructuring of the Ukrainian economy on the basis of innovative approaches to management, mobilisation of Ukraine after its accession to the WTO and on the path to integration into the European Union. Equally important is compliance with the DSTU ISO 9000-2001 Quality Management Systems standard, which regulates the basic principles of quality management at an enterprise in line with international standards and the feasibility of using them to improve business processes.

Optimisation of business processes in the context of international activities is a strategic task of an enterprise, which will ensure the efficiency of the business entity, contribute to increased productivity, and improve the quality of products and services.

Optimisation of business processes in the context of international activities leads to certain advantages for the company, namely: increased investment attractiveness; mutual coordination of the company's strategy with the strategy of foreign economic activity and key performance indicators; timely identification of sources of business risk, reducing its level; reduction of time losses for the implementation of export-import operations; reduction of costs when entering foreign markets; increased flexibility in managing foreign economic activity; creation of an enterprise with a high level of information and defect-free production; certification and standardisation of products in accordance with international standards; employees' understanding of their responsibility for achieving their goals [2].

Optimisation of business processes in the context of international activities can be based on the concept of Business Process Improvement, which is based on four approaches aimed at improving the productivity, efficiency and adaptability of business processes: FAST (Fast Analysis

Solution Technology); benchmarking; redesign (concentrated improvement); and Business Process Reengineering.

Business process reengineering in the context of international activities is:

- a radical upgrade of business processes, which means accelerating the company's response to changes in consumer requirements both in the domestic and foreign markets;
- establishing effective communication and cooperation with foreign counterparties;
- automating the processes of preparing goods for customs clearance;
- cost optimization, which is achieved through the coordinated work of a team of highly qualified and effectively motivated professionals who develop and implement innovative and creative ideas to increase competitiveness, optimize workflows, increase productivity and quality of products and services, and improve customer satisfaction [3].

The concept of business process reengineering has already had and continues to have a revolutionary impact. Nevertheless, the most common mistakes in business process reengineering are:

- the low level of the existing corporate culture of the enterprise, which prevents the adoption of new management principles and causes significant resistance to change;
- unsystematic reengineering, when the enterprise focuses only on partial redesign of existing processes;
- insufficient resource support for reengineering, when the company's management tries to improve the efficiency of operations without significant investments in the reengineering program, without the most important components of investments – time and effort of the most responsible employees of the company;
- ignoring the need for reengineering, which results in significant time and financial losses.

Reengineering is directly related to the use of various business process modelling methods. One of the most modern solutions for modelling business processes in the course of reengineering is the ARIS (Architecture of Integrated Information Systems) functional modelling method, which is aimed at increasing the flexibility of business processes in the context of international activities. The modelling process in ARIS involves collecting information about the area under study, documenting the information obtained, presenting it in the form of a model, and refining the model through iterative review. The purpose of using the ARIS system model is to create the most realistic model of the enterprise's functioning in the face of changes in the internal and external environment, including the international activities of

the enterprise. To this end, it is necessary to take into account all the most probable scenarios. It is worth noting that the flexibility of the ARIS model means that changes and improvements can be made at any time in accordance with the requirements of the environment [4].

As a result, it is found that optimisation of business processes in the context of international activities can lead to the following benefits: the use of a single language for describing activities, accessible and understandable to all participants in the process, will create an opportunity for a simple and clear graphical interpretation of business processes in the field of international activities; allocation of work areas, which facilitates the formulation of requirements for the staff of the foreign economic activity department; simple and reliable definition of control points for achieving strategic indicators of international activities; by reducing the levels of the organisational structure, it simplifies the exchange of information between departments and eliminates the isolation of departments and officials; the ability to assess the effectiveness of operations (functions) performed within a process in terms of the efficiency of the process as a whole; ensuring consistency of the results of operations within processes by avoiding duplication of work and information; reducing overheads and, as a result, the cost of business process results; the possibility of creating a staff motivation system based on rewarding employees depending on the achievement of the results of the processes in which they participate.

Information sources

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